

Iraqi Peer Review Journal ISSN 1817 - 5562

The New Iraqi Journal of Medicine

The Official Journal of The Iraqi Ministry of Health

Volume 1 Number 3 December 2005

The Iraqi Journal of Medicine has agreed the use of the uniform requirements of manuscripts submitted to biomedical journals published by the INTERNATIONAL COMMITTEE OF MEDICAL JOURNAL EDITORS (ICMJE) and it's the first Iraqi peer journal listed by the ICMJE journal list. The first two issues of this journal appeared under the title of Al Karkh journal of Medicine

Executive Editor: Abdul Mutalib Mohammad Ali
Minister of Health

FOUNDING EDITOR: Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi
Member World Association OF Medical Editors

http://www.geocities.com/new_iraqijm

2005 © Postspecialty CME center in the University Hospital in Al-Kadhimiya. Ministry of Health

Our Experience with continuing medical education (CME) programme The CME center, University Hospital in AL-Kadhimiya

Dr.Aamir Jalal AL-Mosawi M.D., Ph.D.,

Physician in charge of Postspeciality CME center.

University Hospital in AL-Kadhimiya.

E.mail:kadhimiyaCME@hotmail.com

www.alkadhimiyaCME.4t.com

E-mail: kadhimiyaCME@hotmail.com

Medicine is witnessing a continuous and tremendous progress in all fields. The enormous strides in the understanding of the bases of diseases have permitted more rational bases for the diagnosis and management of various disorders. New diagnostic tools and new therapies are continuously emerging and contributing to improved patient care and management, and raising the hope for more specific and certain therapy for many disorders. The medical practice is rapidly changing and the aim of the CME center in our hospital is to encourage physicians in our hospital to keep pace with tremendous medical advances and changes in the scientific medical practices in all fields of medicine, So that they can play a critical role in the development of a unique and respectable Iraqi Medicine. Our CME center is encouraging all the scientific activities directed at achieving the above mentioned goal.

The CME programme is currently voluntary. However we have recently propose a scoring (marking) system for the assessment of the CME progress and CME scientific activities for specialist and consultant physicians that can be

used by the physicians themselves or by the directors or by the directors of the physicians in charge of the CME programme. Table (1) Postgraduate Lectures, Seminars, Workshops, conferences and courses aiming at the dissemination of knowledge about the recent advances in various field of medicine are strongly recommended and encouraged. Documentation of all clinical experiences including, the reports of the rare clinical disorders and reports of clinical trials and researches are important contributing factor to the development of medical practices and dissemination of useful medical knowledge.

The New Iraqi Journal of medicine the official journal of the official peer review journal of the Iraqi Ministry of health will help all qualified physicians here and elsewhere in documenting their clinical, research experiences and making it readable and citable outside.

The New Iraqi Journal of Medicine of Medicine is the first Iraqi peer review journal listed by the ICMJE, and currently it the only Iraqi peer review journal printed and distributed by the Ministry of Health.

Table (1): A new scoring system for CME programme achievement

CME activities	Type and setting	Marks(Scores)	Notes
1-Publications in peer review			
Research (clinical study).	In international peer review medical Journal.	70	For multi-author papers the marks are divided by the number of contributors.
	In local Iraqi or Arabian Medical Journal.	40	
Case reports and reviews.	In International medical Journal.	35	= =
	In Local Iraqi or Arabian Journal.		
2-Conferences workshops and symposia			
Made Presentation	International	40	
	Local Iraqi(Arabian)	25	
Attendance	International	20	
	Iraqi and Arabian	15	
3- Lectures(Lectured)	CEM Lectures	10	CEM Lectures should be based on more than 10 references (Journals not books).